

An Automatic Target Cuer/Recognizer for Tactical Fighters

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Abstract -- This paper examines algorithms and techniques for use in a complete FLIR target Cuer/Recognizer. The application is the Air Force Theater Missile Defense Eagle Smart Sensor and Automatic Target Cuer/Recognizer (TESSA) program. The data used for this research are 1st generation FLIR images collected from an F-15E. The database contains thousands of images with various target arrangements. The specific target of interest is a mobile missile launcher, which will be defined as the primary target. The goal is to locate all vehicles (secondary targets) within a scene and identify the missile launchers. The system designed includes an image segmenter, region cluster algorithm, and classifier. Conventional algorithms in conjunction with neural network techniques are used to form a complete ATR system. Some of the conventional techniques include Hit/Miss filtering, Difference of Gaussian filtering, and region clustering. A Neural network (multi-layer perceptron) is used for classification. These various algorithms are tested and combined into a functional ATR system. Overall target detection rate (cuer) is 84% with a 69% accurate primary target identification (recognizer) rate. Furthermore, the false alarm rate (a non-target cued as a target) is only 2.3 per scene. The research will be completed with a 10 flight test profile using an F-15E and will collect 3rd generation FLIR images for use with these algorithms.

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1. INTRODUCTION

With the advance of standoff weapons technology, specifically the ability to fire weapons effectively at longer ranges, it is becoming increasingly more difficult for pilots to positively identify a target in a combat

Figure 1. Example database image

situation. Automatic Target Cueing/Recognition (ATC/R) is of increasing interest to the Air Force. Over the years many topics in ATR have been researched and, depending on the specific application, these individual efforts can be combined into a coherent system that works in unison with existing aircraft systems and weapons [1,2,3,4]. The solution must be affordable, both in an acquisition and maintenance sense. It must also provide an interface that will coexist with existing avionics packages. A simple system to aid the aircrew in the identification of targets is necessary in order to fully utilize the capabilities of these new weapons.

2. ASSUMPTIONS

An example forward looking infra-red (FLIR) image used in the project is shown in Figure 1. Each image in the data set contains one primary target and two other targets. There are also four reference points used for calibration of the sensors. This target configuration knowledge is

not used within the algorithms. The problem presented here is a three class ATC/R problem. A primary target will be defined as mobile missile launchers, and a secondary target will be other vehicles. The third class is any non-target. The reference points are ignored as targets. It will be assumed that the weapon system operator (WSO) has the ability to manually identify a potential target prior to activating the FLIR sensor, thereby increasing the probability of a target being in the sample scene. The last assumption made has to do with the target temperature. The initial focus of the TESSA program was to identify threats in a scene. If a vehicle is ready to fire a weapon it must be running and will be hotter than the background. Cold vehicles can be identified by the algorithm, but that knowledge needs to be provided by the user. For the purposes of this article only warm targets are considered.

Figure 2. Target site examples.(Open, Sparse, Treeline)

3. DATABASE

The FLIR images used in this research were collected from an F-15E carrying a 1st generation FLIR sensor. The target area is located at Eglin AFB, Ft Walton Beach Florida, and these sorties were flown in support of the TESSA project. The original database is made up of “movie” files each of which contain one second of FLIR imagery. This imagery is recorded at 30Hz and each frame is 720x356 in 10 bit gray scale. Each file is broken down into a mission and profile. There were a total of 9 missions, each with about 10 profiles. For each profile one of three target areas was used. These areas were open, sparse, and tree line, all shown in Figure 2.

There are over 5000 frames contained in the database, about half of which have image truth data. The images within a specific target range were of most interest (from about 12km to 3km), and these were the only images truthed. Outside of the upper limit the targets are not visible while inside the lower limit the aircraft is flying directly overhead. One thousand frames were chosen at random and split into a test and training set. The test set has 300 images and the training set has 687. The 13 images excluded from the training set contained invalid image data.

Associated text files contain supporting information collected from each mission, including the target locations and the aircraft orientation and position parameters at the time the frame was taken. This provides the information for a bounding rectangle around each artifact within the image, a vehicle class code, and the range of the image.

The reference points in each image are burning barrels, and are used to calibrate the test instrumentation. These are extremely hot areas in each image and are ignored for this research since these point will not appear in actual application. Whenever the ATR algorithm finds these points in an image it will not score a hit (see Figure 1) nor will it score them misses.

The database has a large variety of image ranges. The images shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4 are from the same mission and target area, taken at different ranges. There is a large disparity in both the target size and orientation.

Figure 3. Long range sample.

Figure 4. Close range sample.

4. ALGORITHM ORGANIZATION

The algorithm is made up of three modules. The first module is the segmenter which is comprised of Hit/Miss and Difference of Gaussian (DOG) filters. The next module is a feature extraction routine. The final module is the classifier which is a multi-layer perceptron (MLP).

The first stage of the process is to run the image through the hit/miss segmenter. This module will pass a region mask (Figure 13) to a clustering routine which will take the mask and

produce clusters of adjoined pixel groups, with the center pixel of each cluster identified. Other features are passed on and will be discussed later. Once the hit/miss mask is finished a Difference of Gaussian filter is applied to the original image. This filtered image is then globally thresholded to produce a second binary mask (Figure 15).

The DOG mask is then segmented to produce a mask that only has information where the hit/miss segmenter found regions of interests. All other areas of the DOG are forced to zero. This final DOG mask is then clustered as in the

hit/miss filter, and region features are extracted from the DOG clusters. The DOG filter is necessary since the hit/miss filter loses some of the shape and energy information from the original image. Only when both filters agree that a region of interest (ROI) exists does the algorithm point out the region as a target.

The final step in the algorithm is to try and define which targets are missile launchers. This module, the classifier, takes the information about the ROI from both the DOG filter and the hit/miss filter and then uses an MLP to decide which class a cluster belongs in. Each of these modules will be discussed in depth. A diagram of the system operation is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Algorithm Structure

5. INITIAL PARAMETERS

At the start of the algorithm several parameters are computed to assist the rest of the modules in detecting and identifying targets. The most important parameter is the estimated target size (which is maximum target length in pixels at a given range). This parameter is based on a linear approximation of measurements taken

from the farthest ranges and others taken from the closest ranges (see Figure 6) and is used to predict the targets size within that scene. Target ranges are provided by additional aircraft sensors and is available in the database. This approximation is designed to err on the long side so all vehicles will be identified and not just those that are the size of the primary target.

Figure 6. Linear Approximation

This linear approximation is only accurate with the target situated such that its longest axis is parallel to the aircraft's line of sight. This orientation produces the longest target length, and that is the number we are interested in here. The actual targets can be much shorter in length if their orientation is rotated from this initial starting point.

Other parameters that are used throughout the algorithm are all computed using this size estimate.

6. HIT/MISS FILTER

The idea of using algorithms that perform well on breast cancer images for FLIR ATR purposes was first discussed in [2] and the results were excellent. The properties of microcalcifications and vehicles at distant ranges were very similar and it was this premise that prompted the use of the hit/miss filter as the primary image segmenter. The hit/miss filter was used by R. Nishikawa [5] to segment breast mammograms. This technique involves applying two filters on the image,

local thresholding, and then comparing these two filtered images for areas of interest.

The first filter applied is a matched filter (Figure 7) which enhances the signal to noise ratio of areas that contain regions that meet a specified size.

Figure 7. Matched Filter

Figure 8. Box Rim filter

For this application the size is determined by the range of the image. Next, a miss filter (box rim, Figure 8) is applied to the original image, and it has the property of reducing the signal to noise ratio. The output of box-rim filter is subtracted from the output of the matched filter to produce an enhanced image. The actual application of the filters and the image subtraction is done in one step by creating an appropriate kernel (Figure 9, Figure 10) and convolving that with the image. In the algorithm the convolution is done in the frequency domain. The resulting filter is a band-pass filter that passes frequencies in the

range of 0.15 to 0.45 of the normalized frequency range of the image [1]. Once the hit/miss kernel is applied it is globally thresholded to produce a hit/miss binary mask.

Figure 9. Hit/Miss kernel (space domain)

Figure 10. Hit/Miss kernel (frequency response)

The original image is then locally thresholded by passing a window (the size of which is determined by the target size approximation discussed above) over the image and computing the standard deviation of that window. If the center pixel of the window is above the local standard deviation by a factor of three, then that pixel in the corresponding position on the local threshold mask is set to one. This produces a binary mask that contains all the regions in the image that have groups of pixels significantly above the mean. The local threshold mask is then pointwise logically

ANDed with the hit/miss mask to produce a segmentation mask. This is done to produce only ROI's that are hotter than the surrounding background.

Figure 11 shows an example of an image before it has been processed by the hit/miss filter. In Figure 12 the image has been filtered with the hit/miss filter and Figure 13 the hit/miss mask has been logically anded with the local-threshold mask to produce the final ROI mask. This is what the ATR system will use to identify the regions of interest. This mask is then passed on to the next stage which is the difference of gaussian (DOG) filter.

7. DIFFERENCE OF GAUSSIAN FILTER

Figure 13 shows that much of the shape and size of the artifacts in the original image have been lost in the hit/miss mask. In order to identify the clusters as targets we need to preserve some of the original shape information. Another type of segmenter used in breast images is the DOG [3]. The DOG is also a bandpass filter. For this application it is used to pass a much wider spectrum than the hit/miss filter [1]. This is done to create a shape cluster of the region of interest for use in the neural network as a feature set. It has the property of showing regions that stand out significantly from the background and will suppress areas that have little contrast. These properties make it a useful tool to extract textures and maintain the structure of the original object in the image.

The size of regions within an image that are highlighted is controlled by the variance of the two non-standard gaussians (Equation 1) that are subtracted.

$$g(x, y) = \frac{1}{2\pi\sigma^2} e^{-\frac{(x^2+y^2)}{2\sigma^2}} \quad (1)$$

Figure 11. Original Image

Figure 12. Hit/Miss filtered image

Figure 13. Hit/Miss binary mask

$$\text{dog}(x, y) = \frac{1}{2\pi\sigma_1^2} e^{-\frac{x^2+y^2}{2\sigma_1^2}} - \frac{1}{2\pi\sigma_2^2} e^{-\frac{x^2+y^2}{2\sigma_2^2}} \quad (2)$$

The subtraction of two gaussians that differ in variance produces equation 2. The form of the gaussian given in equation 1 assures that the filter will be symmetric.

This function produces a filter that has a ring structure in the frequency domain, very similar to the box-rim filter used in the miss filter discussed above. A 2d image of the spatial filter is shown in Figure 14 with the DC term in the center. The size of the frequency ring is determined by the values of σ_1 and σ_2 which in this case are set to 3 and 5 respectively. These parameters, and all the remaining parameters to be discussed, were chosen by genetic algorithm [6].

Figure 14. Frequency response of DOG filter

The application of the DOG filter is a two step process. The first step is to apply the DOG filter to the original image. Since we are concerned with maintaining the shape of artifacts found in the filter the variances are set such that all objects that have potential as targets are found, and their filtered representations closely match the original shape and size of the artifacts in the image. This

produces a filter that has an extremely high false alarm rate when examined by itself. We will use the hit/miss mask to create ROI's within the filtered DOG to eliminate false ROI's. The hit/miss mask is clustered (discussed later) and each cluster is given a center point. Only box regions (the size of which are determined by the range of the image) around these center points in the DOG filter are masked out in the final output (Figure 15). This eliminates areas in the original image that are probably not related to targets. Once this mask has been created it is also clustered like the hit/miss filter, and clusters that correspond to both the hit/miss mask and the DOG mask are taken as potential targets.

By comparing the images above you note that only areas that correspond to both the hit/miss filter and the DOG filter are represented in the final DOG mask. It is from this mask that the features necessary to identify a vehicle are computed.

Figure 15. DOG filtered binary mask

8. CLUSTERING

Once the masks have been created it is important to recognize pixel groups within the mask as individual entities. The first stage in clustering is to define all the areas in the mask

that are adjacent, that is, each pixel group that is fully connected is identified as one cluster. This is done with an 8-way connectivity. The center coordinate, cluster length, and cluster energy (pixel count) are returned to the algorithm. Clusters that are obviously too small or large to be targets for the given range are thrown away. The next step, which is more significant in the identification process, is the grouping algorithm.

The grouping algorithm takes the clusters as a set and compares them in distance and size. In certain circumstances (especially at the closer ranges) a single artifact within the original image is broken into multiple clusters since the DOG mask was not connected in all areas of the cluster. The grouping algorithm looks at the distance between clusters, their main axis lines, and all other clusters along the axis line that are of similar size. If the distance between any two clusters is below a threshold (which is again set by the target range) then the two clusters are grouped as one. The overall length of the cluster is the sum of its constituents as is the overall cluster energy. These clustering routines are done on both the hit/miss mask and the DOG mask individually.

9. MULTI-LAYER PERCEPTRON

Neural Networks have been used very successfully in the past for target recognition [7,8]. The multi-layer perceptron used in this research is a single layer model with 50 hidden nodes and an input layer of seven features (discussed in the next section). The training database generated over 6200 training vectors, thereby providing the structure to support 50 hidden nodes. Fewer hidden nodes were tried, and proved to not generalize as well. The output layer consists of 3 nodes with node 1 representing the primary target, node 2 representing any other vehicle or flash pot, and node 3 represent false targets. A standard

sigmoid is used as the non-linearity function and is applied for both the hidden and output nodes.

The training set was collected by running the ATR algorithm on all the training images, and instead of identifying the clusters the algorithm collects the features from each image, truths the features, and stores this information into a training file that contains labeled training vectors. Training commences with the error surface being minimized given by the mean squared error between the actual output and the desired output [9]:

$$E_r = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{o})^T (\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{o}) \quad (3)$$

where E_r is mean square error, \mathbf{d} is the desired output vector and \mathbf{o} is the output vector given by the MLP. The desired output vector is set by placing a one in the position corresponding to that samples actual class, and a zero everywhere else. Using the above error function the MLP is trained using backpropagation, which is a gradient descent method of learning [10].

The backpropagation learning equation is given by:

$$\omega^+ = \omega^- - \eta \frac{\partial E_r}{\partial \omega}(\omega^-) + \alpha(\Delta \omega) \quad (4)$$

where ω^+ is the new weight matrix, ω^- is the current weight matrix, η is the learning rate, α is the momentum, and $\Delta \omega$ is the change in weight matrix from the previous iteration to the current. For the training of this MLP η is set to

0.1 and α is set to 0.6, and these values are constant throughout training.

The training set consisted of 6236 samples, with 621 of them being primary targets. A problem with random sampling of the training set is the fact that the training set is so unbalanced with the majority of samples coming from the false target class. A method for solving this problem is discussed thoroughly in [11]. Without modifying the sampling rate of each class, the MLP will reduce the overall error by correctly classifying the false targets the majority of time and ignoring the primary class since it is such a small fraction of the samples. To compensate for this a modified sampling rate was supplied to the training algorithm to artificially increase the number of primary classes sampled. The primary and vehicle classes were sampled each 35% of the time with the false target rate set at 30%. This gives the effect of having more of classes 1 and 2, which will allow the MLP to identify these classes more readily. With these modified a priori sampling rates in place, the MLP was trained for a total of 200 epochs and a set of weights extracted for use in the classification algorithm.

10. CLUSTER IDENTIFICATION

Once the clusters have been labeled and the features collected the algorithm identifies which objects in the image are targets, subject to the following assumptions:

- There is at most one primary target per image (tactically motivated)
- All vehicles are of interest as targets
- Targets will be on the average warmer than the surroundings (tactically motivated)

The tactically motivated assumptions come from operational knowledge of the environment. The assumption of a warm target is in place because the main thrust for the TESSA program was to find missile launch vehicles on the move. This implies that the vehicles are running and will be hot. The algorithm works equally well on cold targets but must know ahead of time what type of target it is looking for. An adjustment could be made on the local thresholding routine to look for low intensity clusters instead of high intensity ones. This would be an input from the aircrew on the initial setup of the algorithm. Since the heat information is not available from the database, it will be assumed the targets are warm. Only a handful of images in the database are cold, and these will be discussed later in the results section.

11. FEATURE EXTRACTION

With these assumptions in mind the algorithm looks at the set of clusters from the hit/miss mask and tries to find a cluster in the DOG mask close enough in location to correlate the two as the same artifact. The features used in the MLP are extracted from the regions that have been positionally matched in the hit/miss mask and the DOG mask. The first feature is cluster energy, which is a pixel count of the cluster. The next feature is the cluster perimeter which counts the number of pixels on the outer edge of the cluster. The final feature is cluster length which is a measurement of the cluster distance along its longest axis. These three features are collected from both the hit/miss and DOG clusters which represent the ROI and the range of the image is added to form a seven element feature vector. Range is included not as a target feature, but as an image feature. This allows the MLP to adjust its decision based on the range of the image, since the ROI sizes will change proportional to the range of the image. These values are combined to form a feature set

that the MLP uses to determine the cluster identity. Before the features are used for training or for testing they are normalized using a simple normalization ($\mu=0$, $\sigma=1$). The normalization factors are determined from the training feature set, and these same factors are applied to test vectors as well.

These extracted features are used as inputs to the MLP and an output vector is collected. This vector has three values each representing the possible classes. The value of the output vector represents the probability for each class. A sample output vector is shown below:

[x y z] x = primary, y = vehicle, z = false alarm

The values of the three elements fall between 0 and 1.

Since the MLP was trained with an output of 0 or 1, the sum of the three output nodes is always close to one. The values of these nodes is an approximation of the class probability. The first step in the classification process is to eliminate any clusters which are most probably false alarms. This is done by examining the output for the false alarm class (the third position) and eliminating all the clusters that have a value greater than 0.80 while still having the other two target class values below 0.20. This proved to be a good trade-off between false alarm rate and detection rate. Once those false alarm clusters are removed the remaining clusters are examined for primary identity. The first position of the output vector gives the probability of that cluster being a primary target. If none of the primary class probabilities are greater than 0.5 then it is determined that the image does not contain a missile launcher. All of the remaining clusters are labeled as vehicles.

12. RESULTS

12.1 Introduction

The development of this ATC/R system used two distinct data sets. The first set, which consisted of 687 images, was used as a development and training set. The test set, which contains 300 images, was strictly used to examine the performance and generality of the algorithm. Since the sets are so large only general numbers and trends will be discussed instead of individual images.

12.2 Assumptions

In order to objectively compare the results some assumptions need to be made. One of the most important results is the number of vehicles found in an image. In order for a vehicle to count as a legitimate target it must be entirely on the image. Some vehicles are driving off the edge of the image, and in this case are not totally within the image boundary. When this occurs the vehicle is ignored in the final statistics.

The reference points are also considered not to exist. When the algorithm points these out as target areas it is not scored a hit, and similarly if the algorithm misses a reference point it is not penalized.

12.3 Results

Table 1 shows the raw numbers of targets presented, how many were found, and the percentage of detection.

Table 1. Test data performance

	Vehicle s Present	Vehicles Found	Find Rate
Missile Launchers	292	245	83.90%
All Vehicles (Primaries Included)	857	686	80.05%

Of all the primary targets detected, 69.4% of them were correctly identified as primaries, and the remaining were all identified as targets and were cued as such (this statistic implies that perhaps a different vehicle in the scene was a closer match to the dimensions of a missile launcher).

Table 2. Test set false alarm rate

	#
False Alarms	691
Images Presented	300
Rate	2.30

Table 2 shows the false alarm rate per image. A false alarm is defined as a non-target that is cued as a target. There is a problem with the accuracy of this number since not all of the reference markers were truthed in the original database. All of the reference points not truthed but found by the algorithm are considered false

alarms. The actual rate once these detections are removed is closer to 1.87 false alarms per image. The significant aspect about the false alarm rate is that the majority of false alarms come from the tree line images. Most other images have no false alarms, but the high tree line rate brings up the entire average.

12.4 Result Analysis

It is important to understand why the algorithm misses some primary targets and mis-identifies others. There are several anomalies that make the above results misleading. These occur in the database but under actual conditions either would not occur or could be corrected. This section will identify these anomalies and will present results that correct for these anomalies.

The most significant error is when a missile launcher is present but it is not cued by the algorithm. Since the main objective of this system is to cue all the missile launchers it is imperative that all of the launchers be found. For the remainder of this section an error will be defined as a missed missile launcher (not cued as a target).

12.5 Cold Targets

The most common cause of error is the case when the target is colder than its surrounding area. This causes the target to appear black, and thus its intensity level is below the mean of the image. Since the segmentation module uses a local threshold routine and only hits on areas above the windowed variance it will only tag on areas that are warmer than their surroundings. This was done since the original specification for the TESSA program was for targets that have fired or are about to fire a weapon. This implies that the target is warm, not cold. Figure 16 shows an example of a target area that is colder than its background.

Figure 16. Cold Target

The target outlined on the left of the figure is a missile launcher. The dark line is the actual vehicle and it is significantly colder than its surroundings. The vehicle on the right is warmer than its surroundings and is found by the algorithm. This situation can occur when the vehicle is not running, and it has cooled for a period of time.

To prevent this, the algorithm would need prior knowledge of the type of target. By adjusting the local thresholding routine to point out areas cooler than the background only cold vehicles would be identified. The aircrew may have this knowledge a priori and would be able to set this parameter on the algorithm. The database has no prior knowledge of whether a target is going to be hot or cold. Since the vast majority of all tactical targets are hot the algorithm assumes all targets of interest are warmer than their background.

After removing the images that have cold targets the resulting performance is shown in Table 3.

Of the 300 images tested fifteen were cold target images. This accounts for 4% of the overall error, which is quite significant. This is the most significant cause of error but other factors contributed to the mistakes as well.

Table 3. Corrected results for cold targets

	<i>Vehicles Present</i>	<i>Vehicles Found</i>	<i>Find Rate</i>
Missile Launcher	277	245	88.45%
All Vehicles	817	686	83.97%

12.6 Out of Range

There is a significant limitation to what an ATR algorithm or a human interpreter can do with limited data. Some images in the database were at such great ranges that only 2-5 pixels were on the target at a time. By searching the image for those exact pixel patterns one would find several dozen matches making it impossible for a human or algorithm to identify these as targets from the rest of the background. In a real situation the aircrew can use an expanded field of view on the sensor to enhance an image once a target area is identified, but this imagery is not available in the database. It is unreasonable to penalize the algorithm for insufficient data. An example of a long range image is shown in Figure 17.

Figure 17. Example of an out of range image

The area highlighted contains three vehicles, each averaging three pixels apiece in area. When those same pixel patterns are searched for within the image many exact matches arise.

This makes it impossible for the algorithm or a human to decipher where the targets are without some added information, like expanded views or contextual content. Table 4 shows the results corrected for range.

Table 4. Results corrected for range

	Vehicles Present	Vehicles Found	Find Rate
Missile Launcher	279	245	87.81%
All Vehicles	826	686	83.05%

There were a total of 13 test images that were missed due to range. The adjusted figures again show a large improvement in performance.

12.7 Final Results

Taking the anomalies of data collection out of the initial results we find that the performance of the algorithm is remarkably better.

Table 5. Final corrected results

	<i>Vehicles Present</i>	<i>Vehicles Found</i>	<i>Find Rate</i>
Missile Launcher	264	245	92.80%
All Vehicles	786	686	87.28%

A final detection rate of 93% still leaves 16 primary targets not detected in areas where they should have been found. Most of these errors come from the hit/miss filter being thresholded too high. These can be found by lowering the threshold values, but the false alarm rate becomes unacceptably high.

13. FLIGHT TEST

The final stage of this research is to demonstrate the ATC/R's performance on data collected from 3rd generation FLIR sensors onboard an F-15E. The flight phase will commence in September 1997 and the data will be compiled and published by January 1998. A total of 10 sorties will be flown and a new database will be compiled. Based on the results obtained we expect the new data to perform even better due to the increased signal to noise ratio of the new images.

14. CONCLUSION

The algorithms used for this research have been used successfully for other applications. The initial motivation for using these algorithms was their speed and ease of implementation. The excellent results obtained, especially given such a complex data set, demonstrate the ATC/R characteristics of these algorithms. This is the first ATC/R algorithm that has been built from the ground up to be included into a front-line U.S. weapon system. It shows the diverse nature of these particular algorithms and demonstrates a full ATC/R system that will be implemented in the field. Future plans include a demonstration on 3rd generation FLIR imagery and a hardware implementation that can be installed into a FLIR sensor. These features and algorithms work well with this difficult database. The work done here is a promising first step, which should lead to increased capability with 3rd generation FLIR.

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